

Integrating Universal Generative AI Platforms in Educational Labs to Foster Critical Thinking and Digital Literacy (Supplementary Materials)

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3rd International Conference on Computer Science, Engineering and Artificial Intelligence
(CSEAI 2025) May 30 ~ 31, 2025, Virtual Conference
ISBN : 978-1-923107-60-1

Conference URL: <https://cseai2025.org/index>

IJCI Conference Proceedings, Volume 14, Number 3, June 2025

Proceeding URL: <https://ijcionline.com/volume/v14n3>

Bibhu Dash et al: CSEAI, SCDD, CIOS - 2025 pp. 13-25, 2025. IJCI – 2025

DOI:10.5121/ijci.2025.140302

Presentation Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL1HkUyqULCxy7x8nYFzoqbmJ3XEcdVW2v>

Presentation URL: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15619976>

Lab Manual URL: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15555802

Lab Report Template URL:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pIFWkrvOQwlnuqv2zcVHAC--RL8LJ1k_geglk3W-vU/edit?usp=sharing

Feedback Survey: <https://forms.gle/z8cMQEGfpD8U991u8>

Keywords: #GenerativeArtificialIntelligence, #GenAI, #LargeLanguageModels, #LLMs, #CriticalThinking, #DigitalLiteracy, #AIinEducation, #AIforEducation #AIEducation #education, #ChatGPT, #Claude, #Gemini, #AI-augmentedLearning, #InterdisciplinaryEducation

Students' Creations:

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